

A STUDY ON DEMOGRAPHIC RISK FACTORS CAUSING KIDNEY STONE

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ABSTRACT

Background: Kidney stone disease is a common disease that is estimated to produce medical cost of billions \$ per year in different countries which affecting the population with a peak of incidence around the third to fourth decade of life. Its etiology is related to diet, increase urinary solutes and colloids in hot weather, especially excess of mucoprotein, **Materials and Methods:** A total of one hundred patients suffering from renal stone and hypertension or obesity or both of them. Patients attended Urology Department in Tiktit Teaching Hospital and AL-Harery Teaching Hospital in Medical City, Baghdad. Data were collected through direct interview using a questionnaire designed for patients with kidney stone for this study. A related history was taken and physical examination was done for each patient studied. **Results:** The present study showed that prevalence of renal stone was more in males than

females with frequency of 57 %. The patients with hypertension had the tendency to develop urinary calculi more than the subjects with normal blood pressure as it was concluded by the present study. A BMI gradient trend was observed, with an increasing number of renal stone patients in higher BMI categories, particularly above 30 kg/m², indicating a possible positive relationship between obesity and renal stone occurrence. **Conclusions:** The present study showed that the peak incidence was in the age group 36-50 years old with frequency of 40% of patients. Kidney stone formation was also related to body mass index, family history, blood pressure and family history.

KEYWORDS: kidney stone, demography, models, Iraq.

INTRODUCTION

Kidney stone disease is common disease that is estimated to produce medical cost of 2.1 billions \$ per year in United States only which affecting the population with a peak of incidence around the third to fourth decade of life.^[1] Its etiology is related to diet, increase urinary solutes and colloids in hot weather, especially excess of mucoprotein, decrease urinary citrate, urinary infection, inadequate urinary drainage, and increase serum calcium. There are many types of kidney stones, e.g. calcium oxalate, triple phosphate, uric acid, urate, cystine and xanthine stone. Some kidney stones may be presented with pain, while the others presented with hematuria, pyuria, nausea, uremia and vomiting. Obesity is now one of the most widespread medical problems. Increasing prevalence of overweight and obesity is an important public health problem contributing to significant excess in morbidity and mortality.^[2] The risk factors of obesity are their correlation with many chronic disease like cardiovascular diseases, renal disease, and some metabolic disorder diseases like hyperlipidemia. Hypertension is a leading cause of human cardiovascular morbidity and mortality. It is very common and 25% of the population with a blood pressure above 140/90, usually symptomless, with the potential devastating effects.^[3] Despite the prevalence of hypertension and its associated complications, control of the disease is far from adequate.^[4] Many domestic and international reports have currently focused on the risk factors for renal stone formation. These diverse risk factors including age, gender, race, drugs, genetic, dietary, and environmental factors like occupation and heat exposure as well as drinking water are all reported to be associated with kidney stone prevalence.^[5,6] The incidence of renal stones varies depending on gender, age, geographic location, ethnic background and dietary differences. obesity, Hypercalciuria, hyperoxaluria, insulin resistance diabetes, and other related diseases are common risk factors for stone formation.^[7] Despite these recognized risks, it has been found that patients still have low awareness of kidney disease and its potential safety risks with communication lacking with doctors, which greatly increases the risk of disease.^[8,9] It was found that identifying the risk factors associated with renal stones can serve as a valuable reference for individuals, enabling them to implement preventive measures in their daily lives to reduce the incidence of this condition.

Patients and Methods

Patients

A total of one hundred patients suffering from renal stone and hypertension or obesity or both of them. Patients attended Urology Department in Tiktit Teaching Hospital and AL-Harery Teaching Hospital in Medical City, Baghdad.

Data collection

Data were collected through direct interview using a questionnaire designed for this study. A related history was taken and physical examination was done for each patient studied. The exclusion criteria were patients who underwent catheterization of urethra or ureter and immunocompromised patients. The acceptance for participation in the present study was taken from all the participants whose native language is Arabic. They were not mentally retarded and they were completely healthy considering hearing and speaking.

Statistical analysis

All statistical analyses were carried out following Al-Jebouri and Kaki.^[10,11]

RESULTS

Distribution of renal stone patients according to gender

One hundred patients with renal stone were included in this study and all of them were diagnosed by means of clinical, radiological and ultrasound methods. It was shown that 57% were males (Figure 1).

Figure 1: Renal stone distribution according to gender factor M: male; f: female.

Distribution of renal stone patients according to age

The present study showed that the ages of the patients ranged from 20 to 80 years old (Figure 2). The patients were gathered into three age groups which showed that females of age 50 years revealed the highest incidence of renal stone. Statistical analysis showed no significant difference between age groups ($P > 0.05$) using Chi-square test.

Figure 2: Renal stone distribution according to age.

$X^2 = 1.18^{N.S}$ d.f. = 2 P-value = 0.566 N.S = not significant

Distribution of the renal stone patients according to residence

Figure 3 shows that the incidence of renal stone was more prevalent among males living in urban area. Statistical analysis showed a significant difference between groups of residence ($P < 0.05$) using Chi-square test.

Figure 3: Distribution of the renal stone patients according to residence

$X^2 = 0.507^*$ d.f. = 1 P-value = 0.477 * = significant ($p < 0.05$) level

Distribution of renal stone patients according to blood pressure

The present study revealed that the highest incidence of renal stone was demonstrated among non-hypertensive males (35%) as shown in Figure 4. X^2 Statistical analysis showed a significant difference between the groups with relation to blood pressure ($P < 0.05$).

Figure 4: Distribution of the renal stone of patients according to blood pressure.

$X^2=4.88^*$ d.f. = 1 P-value =0.027 *= significant($p < 0.05$) level.

Distribution of renal stone patients according body mass index

Figure 5 shows distribution of the renal stone patients according to the body mass index (BMI).The patients were gathered into four groups. The probability that a renal stone patient belongs to a specific BMI category was calculated as.

$$P(BMI_i) = \frac{n_i}{N}$$

n_i = number of patients in BMI category i

N = total number of patients

This model allows estimation of BMI-specific burden among renal stone patients. A BMI gradient trend was observed, with an increasing number of renal stone patients in higher BMI categories, particularly above 30 kg/m², indicating a possible positive relationship between obesity and renal stone occurrence. Flow chart of study design and analysis utilized by the present study demonstrated the following descriptive illustration of renal stone with reference to statistical analysis.

Figure 5: Distribution of the renal stone patients according to body mass index

BMI, body mass index

Family history of the patients with renal stone

The present study showed that 28% of patients had a family history of renal stone (Figure 6). Statistical analysis showed a significant difference between the groups (P-value =0.027) using Chi-square test.

Figure 6: Distribution of patients according to family history of renal stone.

$X^2=3.3$; d.f. = 1; P-value =0.027; significant = (p<0.05) level

DISCUSSION

The present study showed that prevalence of renal stone was more in males than females with frequency of 57 %. The ratio between both sexes was almost 1.3:1. This results was almost similar to those of Al-Jebouri.^[12] Obesity and weight gain with high BMI are considered as risk factors leading to the development of kidney stones among susceptible patients,^[13] In the present study, the majority of the patients were obese with high BMI,

indicating that obesity was a significant risk factor for kidney stone formation. However, Taylor et al. found out that obesity may be an independent risk factor for renal stones.^[14] Multivariate analysis revealed that obesity was statistically significantly associated with urinary stones.^[14,15] Moreover, the present study mathematical analysis revealed that the mathematical model.

$$P(BMI_i) = \frac{n_i}{N}$$

allows estimation of BMI-specific burden among renal stone patients. A BMI gradient trend was observed, with an increasing number of renal stone patients in higher BMI categories, particularly above 30 kg/m², indicating a possible positive relationship between obesity and renal stone occurrence. Flow chart of study design and analysis utilized by the present study demonstrated the following descriptive illustration of renal stone with reference to statistical analysis. Furthermore, other studies demonstrated a relation between body fatness and calculi formation.^[16,17,18,19] A positive correlation between BMI and the development of kidney stones was reported in a study carried out by Taylor et al.^[20] and Nowfar et al.^[21] who concluded a direct association between kidney stone formation and obesity in both males and females. However, usually men have more kidney stones than women which is probably due to of the larger muscle mass as compared to women.^[22] The daily break down of the tissue results in increased metabolic waste and a predisposition of stone formation. The other more significant cause is that male urinary tract being more complicated than the female urinary tract.^[23,24,25] Moreover, it might be due to hormonal effect like in experimental animals, when testosterone promotes stone formation by suppressing osteopontin expression in the kidney and increasing urinary oxalate excretion. Estrogen seems to inhibit stone formation by increasing osteopontin expression in the kidney and decreasing urinary oxalate excretion. High urolithiasis inhibitory activity where some authors demonstrated increased urinary citrate concentrations in the urine of women. Moreover, the lower risk of stone formation in women may be due to the lower urinary saturation of stone forming salts.^[26, 27] The present study shows the peak incidence was in the age group 36-50 years old with frequency of 40% of patients. The lowest percentage in the present study was found in the younger group 20-36 with a frequency of 22% of patients. These results were different from those of Al-Jebouri.^[12] Moreover, these result were similar to those found by Baker *et al.*^[28] who reported that the peak age for the development of calcium oxalate stones ranged between 50 to 60 years of age. However, the incidence of stone formation with age may be

correlated with diet and metabolism. The intestinal absorption of many nutrients that influence stone formation, such as calcium, may be reduced in the elderly. In men, the incidence of kidney stones declines markedly after 60 years of age and older stone former is excreted less urinary calcium than their younger counterparts.^[29,30,31] In this study, 78% of the patients were from urban areas (Figure 5). Statistically, there was a significant difference in urinary stone disease distribution according to the residence. These results were almost similar to those found elsewhere^[32] However, locally many people strive for their livelihood by working in construction sites under hot weather where the chances of dehydration are very high.^[33] People are usually careless about their daily water intake. Foods containing oxalate and calcium are regular components of the diet in Iraq; thus, calcium oxalate stones are usually predominant in the country, whereas reports of cystine stones are few. Moreover, high protein intake leads to increased uric acid kidney stones because the acid load in the kidney will markedly elevated due to the amino acid purine a precursor of uric acid.^[34] The patients with hypertension had the tendency to develop urinary calculi more than the subjects with normal blood pressure as it was concluded by the present study. This is because hypertension leads to increase Ca^{+2} excretion in urine and there are two theories to explain this phenomena which are the renal calcium (Ca^{+2}) leak hypothesis which means an increase in urinary excretion of calcium (Ca^{+2}) at each level of sodium (Na^{+2}) output in hypertensive patients. On high salt intake there would be a tendency to sodium (Na^{+2}) retention and as a compensatory mechanism there will be an increase in arteriolar tone (raise the blood pressure) and increase in venous compliance (shift the blood to the center). This leads to expansion in central blood volume without real increment in total blood volume which could cause an increase in urinary calcium (Ca^{+2}) excretion leading to chain of compensatory mechanisms including secondary.^[5] The examination of the patients in the present study revealed that the patients with positive family history having renal stones was 28% and 72 of renal stone patient have no family history with renal stone. This finding was almost similar to those found by other workers^[35,36] It has been found that genetic factor is very important factor in the etiology of urolithiasis.^[37] It was implied that the occurrence of urolithiasis in the same family member may be promoted by living in the same environment along with having similar dietary habits, lifestyles and activities^[38] This emphasizes the contribution of extrinsic factors on stone formation. Nevertheless, genetic susceptibility of renal stone development has been suggested in many researches. Thus people with family history of kidney stones are at higher risk than those without history.^[39,40] Finally, More rigorous attempts with a larger and more representative population size are needed for verifying the results.

CONCLUSIONS

The present study showed that 28% of patients had a family history of kidney stone which was statistically significant. A mathematical model revealed an estimation of BMI-specific burden among renal stone patients. Statistical analysis showed no significant difference between age groups analyzed.

Statement of Ethics

All the procedures involving human participation were conducted in strict accordance with ethical standards of Institutional Research Committee, Department of Scientific Research, Tikrit University as well as the 1964 Helsinki Declaration and its subsequent amendments or equivalent ethical norms.

Data Availability Statement

The data that support the findings of this study are available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request.

Conflict of Interest Statement

The author declares that he has no conflicts of interest, financial or otherwise.

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Financial disclosure

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